

CERTIFICATE OF PUBLICATION

Google Scholar

YEAR: 2024

AD EDUXIAN JOURNAL

ISSN: 3048-7951

**A QUARTERLY MULTIDISCIPLINARY BLIND PEER REVIEWED
& REFEREED ONLINE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL**

This is certified that the Paper Title “Cyber Safety and Security in Digital World” authored by “Dr. Neeta Sahu” has been published in the Volume-(2) Issue-(3) Oct-Dec 2025, ADEJ with PIF:1.024(I2OR) & 3.125(IIFS) with plagiarism free through rigorous blind peer review process in term of originality and quality of work by review committee of ADEJ.

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